

Beyond the Cloud: Democratizing GPU Access for the Digital Humanities with DHInfra.at

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Abstract

This half-day workshop invites DH researchers and developers to shape Austria's next-generation research infrastructure. As demand for specialized AI computing grows, the DHInfra project is deploying federated GPU infrastructure to bridge local hardware limitations and commercial cloud challenges. Inspired by leading HPC centers and advised by EuroCC, we're building a managed, powerful, user-friendly environment.

Timed as a key validation phase before full launch, participants receive early access to infrastructure that has undergone months of rigorous internal testing. Focusing on Large Language Models, attendees will work in prepared containerized environments to fine-tune models and build API-driven workflows. This unique opportunity allows the DH community to test state-of-the-art resources, provide critical feedback, and ensure the platform aligns perfectly with real-world humanities research needs.

Starting Point: The Growing Importance of GPU Computing in the Humanities

The Digital Humanities (DH) have developed rapidly in recent years. While the computational analysis of text corpora remains a central field, research objects and methods are continually expanding. True to the motto of the DHd

2026 conference—"Not just text, not just data"—humanities scholars today work with a variety of data types that require specialized computational approaches. Disciplines such as art history, archaeology, musicology, and film studies generate and analyze datasets ranging from high-resolution image data and 3D models of cultural artifacts and spaces to audio and video data.

This methodological expansion goes hand in hand with the increased use of machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques. Whether it involves automatic transcription of handwritten sources via OCR/HTR, network analysis, or the training and fine-tuning of Large Language Models (LLMs) for specific historical corpora—the demand for (parallel) computing power, as provided by modern GPUs, has risen sharply and is already a prerequisite in some DH projects. However, this development presents the DH community with significant challenges:

Access to Hardware: High-performance GPUs are expensive to purchase and maintain. Few institutions can provide dedicated hardware for the humanities.

Dependence on Commercial Clouds: Services like Google Colab, AWS, or Azure offer seemingly easy access to computing resources but raise serious questions about cost control, data sovereignty, and data protection (GDPR). Sensitive or copyrighted research data often cannot be processed on servers of US companies.

Technical Hurdles: Using High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters often requires specialized technical knowledge (e.g., command-line skills, schedulers, 'hacking'), which is not widespread in the humanities.

There is thus a growing gap between the methodological needs of DH research and the available, accessible, and trustworthy infrastructures (Vogeler and Hofeneder, 2023).

The DHInfra Project: A Sustainable and Collaborative Ecosystem

This is where the DHInfra project comes in. As a broad initiative to strengthen digital research competencies in Austria (see dhinfra.at), it is a core component of the national strategy, operating within the CLARIAH-AT framework to ensure long-term governance and sustainability (Atzenhofer-Baumgartner, 2024).

A key project goal is the deployment of a new, federated GPU platform. The state-of-the-art hardware at both sites in Graz and Krems is already operational. Our expert team is currently executing a meticulous configuration plan based on HPC best practices, implementing a robust software stack built on containerization, orchestration, and scheduling technologies. Internal testing is ongoing to ensure the platform is stable and thoroughly stress-tested well in advance of the workshop. The workshop itself serves as a crucial final step in our rollout strategy: a live, large-scale test to gather invaluable community feedback before the official launch. Our core principles are:

Democratization and Flexibility: An “API-first” approach supports both familiar web interfaces (e.g., Jupyter) and programmatic control. Technologies for Multi-Instance GPUs (MIG) ensure granular and fair resource allocation.

Trustworthiness and Security: As an academic infrastructure hosted in Austria, we offer a secure, GDPR-compliant space for research data (“Go local, go trustworthy”).

Reproducibility and Support: We use standardized rootless containers for reproducible research. To guarantee a successful workshop, we have planned for a decent staff-to-participant ratio, drawing on the wider DHInfra consortium. Our extensive internal testing period and prepared fallback options serve as safeguards for a smooth participant experience.

Intelligent Resource Management: Specialized monitoring software will ensure fair and efficient cluster utilization.

Workshop Goals: From Foundational Skills to Advanced Research

The workshop is structured in two phases and designed to accommodate a range of expertise. Beginners will be guided through structured notebooks, while advanced users can tackle open-ended challenges (Martin, 2024).

Foundations of LLM Interaction: Mastering the Platform: Gain hands-on experience in our pre-configured, reproducible Jupyter environment; Basic Fine-Tuning: Apply Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) to a SOTA base LLM using a custom DH corpus; First API Steps: Learn to programmatically interact with the newly fine-tuned model for simple queries.

Creative and Complex LLM Workflows: Building Advanced Applications: Construct a complete Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system or experiment with Mixture-of-Experts or Multimodal Models that can analyze text and images simultaneously, while critically reflecting on model limitations such as bias, hallucinations, and interpretability (Prescott, 2019; Dubreuil, 2025); Automating Research: Learn to chain multiple API calls to perform complex, multi-step analysis pipelines (e.g., data extraction, analysis, summarization); Community-Driven Development: Provide feedback to shape the future of the DHInfra platform, ensuring it meets the concrete needs of the DH community.

Preliminary Agenda (3,5 hours)

Time	Phase	Content
20'	Welcome and Introduction	Introduction of the organizers and team. Overview of the workshop goals and the vision of the DHInfra platform within the CLARIAH-AT ecosystem.
30'	Demo I: LLM Foundations	Showcase of the core workflow: demonstrating the process of fine-tuning a SOTA base LLM on prepared DH use cases derived from real-world cluster usage and the research scenarios that motivated the infrastructure’s creation. Making first contact via the API.
50'	Hands-on I: Your First Fine-Tuned Model & API Query	In prepared container environments and with prepared datasets, participants fine-tune an LLM. A guided path is provided for beginners, while advanced users can experiment with different configurations, e.g., parameters, memory, compositionality.
20'	Discussion & Coffee Break	Exchange of initial experiences and questions, supported by the full workshop team.
20'	Demo II: Advanced & Multimodal Workflows	Demonstration of building a RAG system and using either a modality-specific (e.g., vision models) or multimodal (e.g. text + vision) LLM for a DH-specific research question.
50'	Hands-on II: Building a Creative Project	Participants choose a track: a guided path to build a RAG system, or an open challenge to design a creative, multi-step (and, if applicable, agentic) workflow using the API. The support team will provide close assistance.
30'	Final Discussion & Outlook	Gathering feedback via a structured questionnaire: What is needed? Which API features are desirable? How can the platform best support LLM-based DH research? Summary and next steps for the DHInfra project; results will be published as a project report.

Target Audience and Prerequisites

The workshop is aimed at all members of the DH community, from students to experienced researchers. Our two-phase structure and high staff-to-participant ratio ensure that both beginners and advanced users will have a productive experience.

Prerequisites: Participants only need a laptop with Wi-Fi access and a current web browser. Programming skills (ideally Python) are an advantage. Curiosity and a willingness to experiment are the most important things to bring. The maximum number of participants is limited to 25 to ensure intensive, personalized support.

Relevance beyond Austria: The workshop addresses general trends in the interconnectedness of HPC and AI systems (such as “AI factories”) and provides transferable knowledge on the use and desiderata for operating large GPU systems—skills and insights applicable to similar infrastructure initiatives across the DACH region and beyond.

Organizers

Florian Atzenhofer-Baumgartner is a PhD student in Computer Science at Graz University of Technology specializing in recommender systems for DH, currently serving as Project Manager for the DHInfra project and Full

Stack Developer in the DiDip project at the University of Graz. With expertise in machine learning, high-performance computing infrastructure, and computational analysis of historical documents, he focuses on developing AI-driven research tools for humanities scholars and maintaining specialized computing resources for DH research.

David Fleischhacker is a Machine Learning Engineer at the University of Graz and Co-Founder/CTO of DeepEx Solutions, currently pursuing his Master of Science in Computer Science at Graz University of Technology. His work focuses on applying machine learning to enhance digital text processing, particularly in historical document analysis, with expertise in OCR technologies and computational methods for digitizing cultural heritage materials.

Max Resch is a Technical Staff Member at the Center for Cultures and Technologies of Collecting at Danube University Krems, Austria, where he leads infrastructure development on DHInfra and specializes in cluster and server infrastructure. His expertise spans computational optimization, DH infrastructure, and digital archiving systems, with research contributions in algorithmic optimization as well as on digital cultural heritage and AI applications.

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